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Survival of the World Trade Organization through Efficient Reforms

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ABSTRACT

The World Trade Organization (WTO) plays a vital role in the international trade community. As of 30 May 2020, 164 states signed the WTO agreement, i.e. USA, China, India, Japan, Canada, Australia, United Kingdom, Newzealand. WTO holds 98% of world trade within the international trade sector. The birth of the World Trade Organization may be traced back to the end of the Second World War. During the Second World War, for economic growth, International Trade Organization (ITO) was formed with the other two intergovernmental organizations (i.e. the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank). ITO could not succeed due to non-ratification of the Havana Charter by the United States Congress. After unsuccessful of ITO, General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) was established to overcome the problems as observed in the ITO. However, the GATT was not free from criticisms due to different factors, i.e. misusing the rules of GATT, 80% of trade transactions were conducted through bypassing the GATT rules among the GATT member states, by not putting the contractual parties on equal footings, providing discriminatory measures towards developing and least developed countries by the developed countries etc). To overcome these obstacles of GATT, WTO came into effect on 1 January 1995. However, the USA claimed that the DSB of the WTO has performed its functions ultra vires and provided judgments against the notion of Article 3.2 of the DSU. Thus, the existence of the WTO is at risk now. Legal scholars, world leaders in G20 Osaka Summit 2019, UNCITRAL's report and the WTO suggested for necessary and efficient reforms of the WTO. This research will examine how efficient reforms of WTO may be achieved from legal and policy perspectives for sustainable economic growth around the world.

INTRODUCTION

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is an essential international trade entity to deal with trade rules among WTO members. World Trade Organization settles the disputes through WTO agreements, negotiation among WTO member states, introducing different treaties/measures among different WTO members etc. The main objectives of WTO are to ensure smoothness, predictable and free trade measures among the WTO members (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/thewto_e.htm).

World Trade Organization was formed on 1st January 1995 through Uruguay Round negotiations (1986-94) (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/thewto_e.htm). WTO is situated at Geneva, Switzerland. As of 30 May 2020, World Trade organization has 164 members like the United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, China, USA, Japan, Russia, New Zealand etc. (Members and Observers, 2020). The WTO represents 98% of world trade and it has a budget of 197 million Swiss francs for 2019. The WTO has 625 secretariat staffs and Roberto Azevedo is the existing Director-General of the WTO (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/thewto_e.htm).

The major decisions of the WTO are decided by its members as a whole, i.e. either by ministers (i.e. meet at least once in every two years), by representatives (i.e. meet regularly subject to necessity). The WTO member states play a vital role in considering important decisions regarding trade-related

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policies or legal measures. The Secretariat of WTO coordinates the WTO activities for the smooth going of the WTO functions. The Secretariat has both staffs and experts (i.e. lawyers, economists, statisticians and communication specialists)

(https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/what_we_do_e.htm).

The main roles of the WTO are to administer WTO's agreements, forming forums for trade negotiations, monitoring trade policies and disputes, providing technical assistance and conduct training for developing states, building networking with other international organizations (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/thewto_e.htm).

Scholars argue the WTO is a successful trade rule-based organization because it can do 10 things, they are summarised as follows (https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/publications_e/wtocan_e.pdf):

- Developing a living standard of the people by taking consideration of different policies;
- Settlement of disputes by compromising trade tensions between WTO members;
- Creating employment opportunities through raising economic growth among WTO members;
- Reducing the cost of doing business internationally among WTO members;
- Encouraging good governance among WTO members;
- Helping countries for the development through boosting up economic growth among WTO members;
- Providing equal bargaining power for negotiation between strong WTO states (i.e. developed countries) and weak WTO states (i.e. developing /least developed countries);
- Supporting the environment and public health by considering environmental and humanitarian objectives/measures;
- Contributing to peace and stability among WTO members by adopting sustainable trade growth and 'Confidential and predictable based policies';
- Be effective without hitting the headlines by adopting proper WTO's routine works and negotiations.

From my point of view, all the above-mentioned points are not exhaustive. The WTO may consider other points subject to its necessity. So, the above-mentioned lists are non-exhaustive list. The words in the WTO preamble like "in accordance with the objective of sustainable development", "need for positive efforts", "to preserve the basic principles and to further the objectives" indicate that the WTO has discretionary powers to consider other essential points besides the above-mentioned 10 points/things for the sustainable development of trade within the world trade community (https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/04-wto.pdf).

The WTO is playing a key role in the global economic governance from its' creation (i.e. 1995). The WTO has settled 500 cases within 20 years (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/dg_e/dg_e.htm). According to the Director-General Roberto Azevedo "*The WTO's dispute settlement system enjoys tremendous confidence among the membership, who value it as a fair, effective and efficient mechanism to solve trade problems*" (https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news15_e/ds500rfc_10nov15_e.htm). The WTO facilitates to boost up the trading capacity of developing and least-developed countries through the multilateral trading system. In another word, The WTO provides preferential trade deals/measures to the poorest countries (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/dg_e/dg_e.htm).

The WTO adopts **new reforms and makes new trade rules** (i.e. Bali Package negotiation during 2013). During 2015, Nairobi package was adopted by WTO for removal of agricultural export subsidies and development of the WTO Information Technology Agreement. In 2017, the Trade Facilitation Agreement came into force for boosting up the world trade by an estimated \$1 trillion each year and this deal provided benefits to the developing and the least developed countries

(https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/dg_e/dg_e.htm).

Amendments of TRIPS Agreement in 2017 provided a gateway for improving access to medicines. During 2017, at 11th Ministerial conference in Buenos Aires, the WTO members adopted a deal for fisheries subsidies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal 14.6 by the end of 2019 (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/dg_e/dg_e.htm).

The WTO follows two key approaches to support economic growth, solving complex disputes, to adopt development procedures, to preserve the rights of WTO members and to create job opportunities for promoting sustainable world development. The two key approaches are as follows (https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/dg_e/dg_e.htm):

- Testing approach: by adopting tried and tested systems among WTO members;
- Sharing approach: by adopting Shared rules and principles among WTO members.

From my point of view, the above-mentioned two approaches are designed to perform the functions of the WTO uniformly by minimizing trade barriers among WTO member states. Thus, we can say,

➤ Testing Approach + Sharing Approach = Uniform Approach

From the above discussion, it may be observed that WTO may adopt reforms and new rules. Before discussing the necessity of reforms for WTO, we require to get an overview of the historical background of WTO. In the next session, I will discuss the historical background of WTO.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF THE WTO

During the Second World War, it became necessary to establish intergovernmental organizations for the sustainable development of economies around the world. Based on this notion, three intergovernmental organizations were formed, i.e. International Monetary Fund (IMF), the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank), International Trade Organization (ITO). International Trade Organization (ITO) could not come into force in consequence of the non-ratification of the Havana charter by the United States Congress (Steger, 2010).

Because of the non-existence of ITO, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) was formed through 'negotiated combine support' from the different states. GATT came into effect through a protocol of provisional application which provided guarantees for its future existence. GATT was successful for expansion of its memberships due to its attractive trade mechanisms, i.e. successful multilateral trade negotiations procedure, equal opportunities for access to the trade market, improved version of the dispute settlement system (Steger, 2010).

The GATT was not excluded from the criticisms owing to its different procedures/measures/policies, (https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/168133/10/10_chapter%203.pdf) i.e.

- A large number of the GATT members excluded or bypassed the application of GATT rules in their contracts which were formed among GATT members;
- The GATT emphasized on special treatments for agriculture products. But, most of the developed nations adopted agricultural trade policies which were against the GATT rules;
- Developed member states of the GATT eliminated partial trade barriers (i.e. not full elimination). These countries adopted different new trade barrier measures which were beyond the GATT rules, i.e. voluntary export restraints, low-cost supplies, market disruption. These restrictive measures applied to the developing countries including Japan. These restrictive measures affect 50% and 45% of the French and USA imports' markets respectively;
- The GATT members introduced 'different bilateral and discriminatory treaties' and restrictive measures which were inconsistent with the GATT rules. These discriminatory measures restricted developing countries to export products to developed countries;
- Misuse of "subsidies measures" according to the GATT rules;

- Misuse of "safeguard" rules under Article XIX of the GATT by converting these temporary restrictions to permanent features within the world trade system;
- The GATT member states were permitted to establish customs unions and free-trade areas according to the Article XXIV of the GATT rules. However, due to ambiguities, the Article XXIV of the GATT rules were abused by the GATT member states;
- The GATT rules were difficult to implement as a mandatory body for its **non-binding effect** on the GATT rules;
- Due to these ambiguities, 80% of world trade transactions were conducted bypassing the GATT rules.

Because of the above-mentioned shortcomings, the GATT failed to achieve its real goal and so then the GATT was replaced by the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995. WTO may be traced back from the Uruguay Round Declaration where ministers agreed to a 'declare on achieving greater coherence in global economic making'. Uruguay Round Declaration strengthened the 'cooperation relationship' of the WTO with the IMF and the World Bank. The WTO was established through Article III of the Marrakesh Agreement (Steger, 2010). This is how WTO came into existence in the international trade community.

As stated before, the WTO may adopt new reforms and new policies. In the next session, I will provide a brief idea of how scholars have suggested or provided ideas for the reforms of the WTO.

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE WTO'S REFORMS FROM SCHOLARS' CONTEXTS

Different world leaders, international organizations, scholars suggested for the reform of the current WTO. I will briefly explain their thoughts in the next paragraphs.

From world leaders contexts, in G20 Osaka Summit 2019, World leaders argue for free, fair, non-discriminatory, transparent, predictable, stable trade and better investment environment and free market for the sustainable growth of trade within the world trade community. These issues will boost world economic growth and create job opportunities. Finally, the world leaders in the G20 summit suggested: "We reaffirm our support for the **necessary reform** of the World Trade Organization (WTO) to improve its functions" (<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/06/g20-summit-2019-latest-updates-190624071602768.html>).

From the international organizations' perspective, as per the UNCITRAL's report, the UNCITRAL stated: "*the progress of the multilateral trading system as established by a "provisional" agreement less than 70 years ago and developed spectacularly by what has become the WTO system, a network of a wide range of regulations has now at best **slowed down significantly, at worst** come to a **standstill**".* UNCITRAL also suggested choosing other international trade laws (i.e. CISG) for conducting international trade transactions more efficiently. This idea facilitates the application of WTO and CISG together (https://www.uncitral.org/pdf/english/texts/sales/cisg/35_Years_of_Uniform_Sales_Law-E.pdf). This new approach may be termed as "fusion of CISG and WTO". The application of CISG along with WTO will be briefly outlined under the heading of the WTO's reforms from the legal perspectives.

For example (Sipahi, 2020) study identifies the impact of tax planning on the firm value of consumer goods manufacturing companies in Cyprus. The specific objectives are to determine the impact of firm and leverage on firm value of Cypriot consumer goods manufacturing companies. The data included in the study were collected from the annual reports and accounts of consumer goods of the manufacturing companies in Cyprus and formulated hypotheses were tested with multiple regression analysis.

From the WTO context, The Director-General Roberto Azevedo commented ***“Reform is already happening.....The Challenges we have before us will not be tackled overnight- or over a few months. We are in for a rather long journey. But I believe it is one that is unavoidable. Staying where are is not an option. In fact, the journey has already begun, where one realises this or not. So let’s seize this opportunity to update and strengthen the system”*** (https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news19_e/tnc_19jul19_e.htm).

From the USA perspective, Administration of Donald J. Trump stated *“May be the WTO was worse. The WTO, from the time that happened in '95-from the time that happened, China became like a rocket ship. It was pretty much flatlined, and then, all of a sudden, they joined the WTO, and they became-they went-I mean, they went through the roof. And very much to our Liability, it's-we lost tremendous amounts of money over the-from that time. I mean, we just lost tremendous amounts. It was a terrible deal, the WTO, World Trade”* (<https://heinonline.org/>).

Scholars pointed out that Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) of WTO is at risk. Appellate Body (AB) of DSB should have seven members. But, now there are only three members out of seven members. On December 2010, it was known that two members out of three members’ contracts of appointments came to an end. (<https://www.jurist.org/commentary/2020/04/rathore-bajpai-wto-appellate-body-crisis/>). It will be advisable for the WTO for the quick reform of DSB to save the WTO from future non-existence.

Donald J. Trump expressed the opinion that DSB of WTO acted beyond its jurisdiction and it will impact on the binding effect of DSB judgements on the WTO member states [14]. USA pointed out that DSB has acted as noncompliance way according to Article 3.2 of the DSU (i.e. can not add to or diminish the rights and obligations provided in the covered agreements) (<https://www.jurist.org/commentary/2020/04/rathore-bajpai-wto-appellate-body-crisis/>). These consequences may trigger the USA to withdraw its membership from the WTO (<https://www.kalerkantho.com/print-edition/industry-business/2019/09/04/810701>).

Japan suggested for the WTO’s reforms by considering different issues(i.e. developing DSB, promoting transparencies and accountabilities etc.) and measures (i.e. equal footing approach, developing digitalised commerce platforms etc. (Yueju, 2019).

The European Union (EU) also argued for the prompt reforms of the WTO by adopting different trade policies for developing trade relationship between the EU and non-EU countries (Yan, 2019).

From the above discussion, it may be examined that the urgent reforms of WTO are necessary to save the WTO from its’ future non-existence. The readers may be keen to know how reforms of WTO may be achieved. In the next session, I will illustrate how different measures (i.e. from legal and policy perspectives) may be considered for the achievement of potential reforms of the WTO for WTO’s future survival.

THE WTO’S REFORMS FROM LEGAL AND POLICY PERSPECTIVES

Reforms of the WTO may be considered by examining different approaches from both legal and policy perspectives. In the next subheadings, I will separately explain how legal issues and policy measures will be dealt with for the reforms of the WTO.

The WTO’s reforms from the legal perspective

From a legal perspective, we need to examine how different legal rules may be applied to achieve potential reforms of the WTO.

Firstly, we need to consider as to whether the WTO has jurisdiction to adopt other international laws to fill up the WTO's legal loopholes. In ***Gasoline*** case, the Appellate Body of the WTO commented the WTO is not separate from international laws. This notion suggested, the WTO may adopt other international laws with WTO rules (<https://heinonline.org/>).

In ***Lockerbie*** case, the International court suggested, the WTO may consider the adoption of other international laws (i.e. Montreal Convention). This decision opened the gateway for the WTO to consider different international laws (i.e. CISG, UNCLOS III, Vienna Convention etc) (<https://heinonline.org/>).

Considering the example of the practical application of the CISG's provisions on the WTO rules, we may observe, Article 6 (i.e. enable the contracting parties to tailor the provisions of CISG to meet their requirements for their sale contracts) and article 9 (i.e. enable contracting parties to consider any usages and practices trade laws for the settlement of their contractual disputes) of CISG provide opportunities to the WTO members to apply CISG alongside the WTO rules. This is known as "fusion of CISG and WTO" as stated earlier (<https://www.uncitral.org/pdf/english/texts/sales/cisg/V1056997-CISG-e-book.pdf>).

The above-mentioned practical example allows a gateway for the application of other international trade laws alongside the WTO rules which will be a fruitful initiative for the efficient reforms of the WTO.

In the next subheading, readers will get an idea of how adopting policies will contribute to the reforms of WTO.

The WTO's reforms from the policy perspective

From the Policy perspective, readers will be given ideas about how different nations have pointed out different policies for the reforms of the WTO.

The WTO member states are facing difficulties to settle the disputes through the DSB of the WTO due to controversial issues. During this critical situation, the WTO member states may observe the different WTO's members' policies to cope up the current situation.

On July 25, 2019, Canada and EU jointly adopted an ad-hoc Arbitral body (Interim Appeal Arbitration Arrangement) to settle their disputes despite the direct involvement of the DSB of the WTO (<https://www.mondaq.com/canada/international-trade-investment/832124/canada-and-the-eu-agree-to-wto-dispute-settlement-work-around>). The WTO members may introduce different self-arbitral tribunals subject to the consent of the contractual parties to solve the disputes besides the DSB to tackle the current situation.

Until 29 May 2020, WTO received 144 notifications concerning COVID-19. The WTO suggested this is the crucial time to deal with the matters during COVID-19 pandemic (https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/covid19_e/covid19_e.htm). From my point of view, WTO should introduce and adopt well equipped digitalised platforms (i.e. online services) to cope with the COVID-19 pandemic.

From the above discussion, the readers have got views on how the WTO reforms may be achieved from legal and policy contexts. In the next session, I will briefly outline my recommendations to the readers for the efficient reforms of WTO.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From my point of thought, the WTO should be recommended for the reforms of the WTO by taking consideration of the following non-exhaustive points:

- Forming the “Reform Council (RC)” for the WTO which will be formed with all the necessary expertise. It will be the central council to deal with the WTO reforms’ mechanism. The Director-General of WTO will be the head of the Reform Council;
- Adopting “Microscopic Approach” to find out the real obstacles/problems (A-Z) for the survival of the WTO and point out the solutions for those loopholes;
- Forming the “Revision Council (RC)” for the WTO which will revise and examine all the WTO rules. Revision Council will refer its finding (i.e. amendments of the rules of the WTO to cop with current international trade situation and develop the WTO rules to ‘up to date’) to Reform Council;
- Creating the “Research Council(RC)” for the WTO which will perform research on how efficiently reforms of the WTO may be achieved. The prime research should be focused on how the DSB will be more efficient to perform DSB’s functions by putting the WTO members on equal footing for the settlement of disputes. Research Council should also research how preferential/special treatments may be provided more efficiently to the developing and the least developed countries;
- Forming the “Liaison Committee(LC)” for the WTO which will act as a “friendly communication bridge” between the WTO and the WTO member states. The Liaison Committee will collect the pieces of information and suggestions from the WTO member states for the potential reforms of the WTO. The LC will send all the pieces of information to the Research Council to conduct research on different suggestions which were gathered from the different WTO member states. After getting the pieces of information from the LC, the Research Council should conduct research based on “interest as a whole” which will benefit all the WTO members equally. After conducting research, Research Council will pass their “research-based suggestions” to the Reform Council for the final scrutinization and adoption of recommendations;
- Creation of the “Fund Raising Committee(FRC)” for the WTO which will work as to how huge funds for the potential reforms of the WTO may be arranged. It will work alongside the Research Council and the Liaison Committee. Funds arrangements’ reports should be delivered to the Reform Council to examine and consider the funds’ arrangement procedures.

Finally, the day is not far way when it will be an “alternative essential option” for the WTO to prepare for the efficient reforms of the WTO for its survival subject to the extension of the reforms (i.e. it is a question of fact and depends on circumstantial pieces of evidence/issues/situations), necessities and jurisdictional capacities. Efficient reforms of the WTO will facilitate to develop or promote sustainable economic growth within the world trade community.

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